

Quality Attributes of Foreign and Locally Made Ankara Fabrics Among Civil Servants in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Research Article

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ABSTRACT

Ankara fabric is a symbol of traditional cloth of high quality among the Yoruba. This observation led to the study of low patronage of Ankara fabric for office wear. This study examined quality attributes of Ankara fabrics (foreign and local). This study adopted a cross-sectional research design; 230 respondents from Ministries and extra-Ministerial Agencies (MDAs) in Ekiti State were randomly selected using a multi-stage sampling technique that involved random selection of eight (8) MDAs. Data were obtained through a closed-ended questionnaire and analysed using frequency counts, percentages, chi-square, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). Findings show that 57.3% of employees in the study area were female, 76.5% were married, 91.7% were Christians, and 49.2% had postsecondary education. Quality attributes of foreign Ankara fabrics were ranked from highest to lowest mean score: colour fastness (\bar{x} =3.45), texture (\bar{x} =3.38), colour fastness (\bar{x} =3.78), thread count (\bar{x} =3.33), durability (\bar{x} =3.27), fabric finish (\bar{x} =3.23), abrasive strength (\bar{x} =3.20), fabric density (\bar{x} =3.18), feel and drape (\bar{x} =3.16), fabric width (\bar{x} =3.13), fabric weight (\bar{x} =3.13) crease and wrinkle resistance (\bar{x} =3.13) and air permeability (\bar{x} =3.09). The quality attributes of local Ankara fabrics were ranked from highest to lowest mean score: weave (\bar{x} =3.00), air permeability (\bar{x} =2.87), fabric weight (\bar{x} =2.82), texture (\bar{x} =2.82), colour fastness (\bar{x} =2.81), feel and drape (\bar{x} =2.81), fabric finish (\bar{x} =2.76), thread count (\bar{x} =2.75), abrasive strength (\bar{x} =2.75), fabric density (\bar{x} =2.71), durability (\bar{x} =2.70), fabric width (\bar{x} =2.65), crease and wrinkle resistance (\bar{x} =2.63). The study concluded that Ankara fabrics local and foreign should be encouraged among Civil Servant as office wear throughout the federation in order to support the local manufacturing sector and the emerging fashion designers.

Keywords: Quality, Attribute, Ankara, Fabric, Office wears.

1 Introduction

Ankara, commonly known as “Ankara prints,” “African prints,” African wax print,” “Holland wax” and” Dutch wax” a 100% cotton fabrics with vibrant patterns, Ogunduyile, (2022). Ankara, an Indonesian cloth, is renowned for its colorful cloth with tribal-like patterns, crafted using batik, an Indonesian wax-resist dyeing technique, ensuring distinct patterns (Billie, 2014). The fabric company ensures quality and protects designs with registration numbers on selvage. (Solanke, 2016). Ankara fabric, a versatile fabric, conforms to local preferences, with colours tailored to local preferences. This fabric is a formal choice for special occasions, contributing to job creation, foreign exchange generation, and societal well-being through industrialization. One of the biggest industries in

the world is that of textiles and apparel (Odey et al., 2018); (Olushina, 2014). Fashion brands and fabric suppliers have manufactured versatile Ankara prints on fabrics like chiffon, silk, and spandex, enhancing the versatility of their clothing products, including kaftans, bathing suits, and leggings. (Willie, 2020). Some people wear Ankara fabrics as “Aso ebi” “, clothes of the family” for special occasions such as /birthdays, weddings, church/mosque programs, among others. Aso ebi is a cloth that is chosen, sewn into garments, and worn by groups of individuals who are related in various ways, such as family, friends, or comrades (Billie, 2014). Ankara fabrics outfits are worn for social occasions known as Owambe which is a term used to describe social gatherings, particularly parties, (Orimolade, 2014). Even though Ankara fabrics origins are not authentically and wholly African but with an Indonesian cloth, its patterns are associated with the African culture (Olayemi, 2018).

Research indicates that personal identities have a stronger impact on self-concept formation than social identities, even in collectivist cultures. (Gaertner et al., 2012). Clothing culture is considered as a symbol which communicates meaning like languages do. From linguistic and anthropological point of view, Olaoye and Bello, (2016) opined those corporate institutions in Nigeria exhibit a unique dress culture that reflects their national identity. The attire worn to the office reflects personal style and fashion consciousness, reflecting exposure to current trends in the fashion world. A crisp, neat attire is essential for a presentable and decent appearance. According to Newbern (2001) a full matching business suit which includes a jacket, dress pants, or a dress skirt is the required attire for formal business settings. A person's appearance can reveal more about them than their profession or title, according to Wilde (1890) “Only the casually inclined do not base their decisions on appearances”. In a larger sense, the psychology of stylish clothing reflects our innermost thoughts and feelings, serving as a lens through which others perceive us, causing confusion when there's an incongruity between appearance and person. (Lilli, 2018). Establishment images are essential for projecting an appealing image, and wearing appropriate attire is crucial for a professional and captivating work environment, fostering a positive and productive work environment. (Juneja, 2021). Corporate attire significantly influences first impressions, with body language, facial expressions, and overall appearance shaping people's perceptions. The visual impact of these elements, alongside verbal influence, significantly influences the overall impression of an individual. Ogunnaike (2010) assert that Ekiti State's consumers are increasingly choosing foreign products due to unawareness and timidity, leading to a preference for superior quality and lower prices. This trend is evident in employees' preference for foreign fabrics in office attire, affecting local fabric manufacturing and contributing to the decline of domestic products. Though the use of Ankara fabric had been finite to traditional attires such as Agbada, buba and sokoto, Iro and buba, ‘Aso-ebi’ among others. They are mostly not used for office wear such as shirts, skirts and blouses, blazers, trousers, to mention but a few. Despite the fact that Ankara fabrics are largely accepted as local clothing but not as workplace attire, this has decreased their use in the offices. Foreign products are often preferred over domestic products due to their perceived value and expressiveness, leading to increased consumption of imported products. (Hult, 2012). Therefore, the problem of this study is low usage of Ankara fabrics as office wear by the public employees in Ekiti State.

1.1 Research Objectives

- a. Ascertain the socio-economic characteristics of employees in the study area.
- b. Compare and contrast the quality attributes of foreign and locally made Ankara fabrics as office wears

The hypotheses of this study are slated in null form as follows:

- a. Ho1: There is no significant difference between the quality attribute of foreign
- b. Ankara fabrics and quality attributes of locally made Ankara fabrics
- c. Ho2: There is no significant differences in the use of foreign and locally made Ankara fabric as office wear between male and female employees

2 Research Methodology

2.1 Research Design

Cross cross-sectional survey design was used for the study. The data were collected from the respondents at a single point for the period of the study.

2.2 Description of the Study Area

Olubummo (2014) opined that Ekiti State, southwestern Nigeria, is a homogeneous state with distinctiveness. Ekiti State, is a subgroup of the larger Yoruba ethnic group and is renowned for its diverse traditional music, poetry, and arts. The National Population Commission (NPC, 2006) reported a population of 2,384,212 people in Ekiti State, which is characterized by its diverse dialects. The state is situated on hills and valleys, with over 127 towns and well-linked roads. The state is divided into sixteen Local Government Areas.

2.3 Population of the Study

Table 1: Sampling frame of the study (n=230)

S/N	NO OF MDAs	Population for each MDA	Total number of employees sampled
1	State Environmental Protection Agency	27	19
2	Bureau of Public Procurement	52	36
3	Ekiti Scholarship Board	16	11
4	Cabinet and special service Department	41	29
5	Judicial Service Commission	48	34
6	Fountain Agric. Marketing Agency	43	30
7	Ekiti State Local Government Staff Loans Board	83	58
8	Ekiti State Emergency Management Agency	25	18
	TOTAL	335	235

Source: Field Survey, 2023

2.4 Sample Size

Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) sample size chart for finite population was used as a total of 335 was used for this study. From the chart for a population of 340, a minimum sample size of 181 is required. "However, in other to account for lost or un-retrieved questionnaires". 30% of the sample size was added. This is approximately 54. Thus, a sample size of $(181+54) = 235$ was used for the study.

2.5 Sampling Technique

A multistage sampling procedure was used to select respondents for this study. The stages are indicated as follows:

- i. **Stage 1:** The first stage involves the selection of employees in (Ministries/ Extra-Ministerial Department) in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Out of the seventy-nine (79) MDAs in the Ekiti State, eight (8) MDAs were randomly selected and this is due to proximity to each other;
- ii. **Stage 2:** As indicated in Table 1, the selected MDAs are, State Environmental Protection Agency, Bureau of Public Procurement, Ekiti Scholarship Board, Cabinet & Special Services Department, Judicial Service Commission, Fountain Agric. Marketing Agency, Ekiti State Local Government Staff Loans Board and Ekiti State Emergency Management Agency. Watson, (2001) sampling technique at a 95% confidence level with an estimated 75 variance in population (the degree of variability) was used to select 70% of the employees in the MDAs as shown in table 1
- iii. **Stage 3:** Stratified sampling technique was used to group the respondents into male, female, senior and junior staff.
- iv. **Stage 4:** Simple random sampling was used to select the respondents.

2.6 Method of data collection

Structured questionnaire was used to gather data from the respondents. The questionnaire was divided into five (5) sections.

- i. **Section A** determined the socio-economics characteristics of respondents such as age, gender, marital status, religion, educational and economic status.
- ii. **Section B** measure objective 2 and focus on the quality attributes of Ankara fabrics (Local and foreign) as office wear. The attributes are weave, colour fastness, thread count, durability, abrasive strength, fabric weight, feel and drape, fabric finish, fabric width, fabric density, texture, crease/ wrinkle resistance and air permeability. A 4-point rating scale of excellent, good, fair and poor was used to compare and contrast the quality attributes between foreign and locally made Ankara fabrics with a score of 4,3,2,1 respectively.

2.7 Method of Data Analysis

Data was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics which include: frequency counts, percentages and tabular representations of data and variables were used to analyse the objectives of the study while inferential statistics such as Pearson Product Moment Correlation, Chi-square, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to analyse the hypotheses using statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 21.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Socio- Economic Characteristics of the Respondents

Table 2 revealed that 33.5% of the respondents were 30 years and below, 26.5% were 41–50 years and 25.7% were between 31–40 years while 51years and above were 14.3%. This implies that most of the respondents were in their active age. This is supported by Zacher et al. (2017) who reported that studies in the field of work and aging include workers between career entry (typically sometime between 15-25 years) and retirement entry (typically sometime between 60-70 years), thus inferring that the respondents in this study are within the working or active age. The result also revealed that most (91.7%) of the respondents in the study area were Christians while 7.4% were Muslims and 0.9% were traditional worshippers. The result displayed on Table 2 showed that most of the respondents were married (76.5%), single (18.7%) widowed (3.9%) and only 0.9% were divorced. The high percentage of married people is an indication that most of the respondents have responsibility in the preference of Ankara fabrics (local and foreign) as office wear among employees in the study area. Furthermore, (49.2%) of the respondents had tertiary education (first degree), 24.3%

had HND (first degree) and 14.3% had OND/NCE certificate, 7.0% had M.Sc postgraduate qualification, while 5.2% had secondary school certificate. The result indicated that all the respondents were literate and they are on different level of western education. Table 2 also revealed that 52.2% of the respondents had less than or equal to 10 years work experience. 30.9% had between 11–20 years of work experience, 18.7% had 21 and above years of work experience. This indicated that most respondents had good working experience that could influence their preference of Ankara fabrics (local and foreign) as office wear in the study area. Also table 3 revealed that Rank/status ($p= 0.161$) is significant, religion ($p= 0.392$) is also not significant, sex ($p= 0.030$) is significant, marital status ($p= 0.207$) is not significant, educational status ($p= 0.012$) is significant. Age is significant ($p= 0.013$), with an r -value of -0.180 . Size of household ($r= 0.040$), not significant ($p= 0.676$) monthly income ($r= -0.206$) was significant furthermore, ($p= 0.052$) was also significant; year of experience ($r= -0.007$), ($p= 0.933$) not significant.

Table 2: Socio-economic characteristics of employees (n=230)

	Variable	Frequency	Percentage	Means (\bar{X})
Age (years)	< 30	77	33.5	38.5 years
	31-40 years	59	25.7	
	41-50 years	61	26.5	
	51 and above	33	14.3	
Sex	Male	98	42.6	
	Female	132	57.3	
Marital	Single	43	18.7	
	Married	176	76.5	
	Divorced	2	0.9	
	Widowed	9	3.9	
Education	SSCE	12	5.2	
	OND/NCE	33	14.3	
	HND	56	24.3	
	B.SC	113	49.2	
	M.Sc	16	7.0	
Status	Senior	193	83.9	
	Junior	37	16.1	
Household Size	Less than or equal to 3	139	60.4	
	4-5	80	34.8	
	7 and above	11	4.8	
Work Experience	< or = 10	116	50.4	10 years
	11-20 years	71	30.9	
	21 and above	43	18.7	

Religion	Christianity	211	91.7	
	Islam	17	7.4	
	Traditional	2	0.9	
	30,000 -	181	78.7	
	50.000	37	16.1	N48,841k
	51000-	12	5.2	
Monthly Salary	100.000			
	> 100.000			

Source: Field Survey, 2023 Standard Deviation (SD).

Table 3: Socio-economic characteristics of employees (n=230)

Variables	p=(Value)	r=(Value)	Results
Rank/status	(p= 0.161)		significant
Religion	(p= 0.392)		not significant
Sex	(p= 0.030)		Significant
Marital status	(p= 0.207)		not significant
Educational status	(p= 0.012)		Significant
Age	(p= 0.013)	r=value of -0.180	not Significant
Size of household	(p= 0.676)	(r= 0.040)	not significant
Monthly income	(p= 0.052)	(r= -0.206)	Significant
Year of experience	(p= 0.933)	(r= -0.007)	not significant

3.2 The result of the hypothesis

There are no significant differences between respondents and their perception of the choice of Ankara fabrics as office wear. The test was conducted using the Chi-Square test for the variables measured at the nominal level, while, Pearson product-moment Correlation (PPMC) was used for variable at the interval level, and the result is presented in Tables 4 and 5.

This is an indication that the difference in the gender of the respondents, that is, some of the respondents been male while others are female influences their choice of Ankara fabrics as office wear. Furthermore, for (PPMC) result socio-economic such as age, household size, years of experience and monthly income were imputed in the model the significance of relationship was determine at 0.05 level the correlation analysis shows that there was a negative and significant relationship between respondent age ($r = -0.180$, $p = 0.013$) monthly income ($r = -0.206$, $p = 0.050$) and their perception of the choice of Ankara fabric as office wears.

Table 4: Chi-Square test of association between socio-economic characteristics (Sex, marital status, educational status, rank/status and religion) and preference for Ankara fabric

S/N	Variables	Chi-Square Value	Df	P-Value	Decision
1	Sex	4.694	1	.030	Significant
2	Marital Status	4.5567	3	.207	Not Significant
3	Educational Status	12.934	4	0.012	Significant
4	Rank/Status	3.652	2	1.161	Not Significant
5	Religion	1.874	2	.392	Not Significant

p Value ≤ 0.05 Significant

r Value > 0.05 Not Significant

Table 5: Pearson correlation test of association between socio-economic characteristics (age, household size, year of experience and monthly income) and preference of Ankara fabric.

s/n	variable	Correlation(r)	Value p-value	Decision
1	age	-0.180	0.013	Significant
2	Household size	0.040	0.676	Not Significant
3	Years of experience	-0.007	0.933	Not Significant
4	Monthly income	-0.206	0.050	Significant

P Value ≤ 0.05 Significant

r Value > 0.05 Not Significant

3.3 Ankara fabric selection, purchase frequency and garment construction

The result presented in Table 6 showed the distribution of the Styles and Selection of Ankara fabrics. From the result, about 76.9% of the respondents claimed that they usually select Ankara fabrics by self, 60.4% of the respondents claimed that they buy Ankara fabrics every six month on an average, 53% of the respondents claimed they sew Ankara fabrics every six month, 21.7% of the respondents claimed they sew Ankara fabrics every month, 19.6% of the respondents claimed that they buy Ankara fabrics every month, 18.7% of the respondents claimed that their spouse usually select Ankara fabrics on their behalf, 15.2% of the respondents claimed that they buy Ankara fabrics after a year, 13.5% of the respondents claimed they sew Ankara fabrics after a year, 11.7% of the respondents claimed they sew Ankara fabrics weekly, 4.8% of the respondents claimed that they buy Ankara fabrics weekly, and 2.6% of the respondents claimed that their children select Ankara fabrics on their behalf, while 1.7% of the respondents revealed that their friends select Ankara fabric for them.

Table 6: Selection of Ankara fabric, frequency of purchase and construction into a garment (n=230)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage %
Who usually selects your Ankara fabrics for you?		
Self	177	76.9
Spouse	43	18.7
Children	6	2.6
Friend	4	1.7
On average, how often do you buy Ankara fabrics?		
Weekly	11	4.8
Every month	45	19.6
Every six months	139	60.4
After a year	35	15.2
On average, how often do you sew Ankara Fabrics?		
Weekly	27	11.7
Every month	50	21.7
Every six months	122	53
After a year	31	13.5

3.4 Quality Attributes of Local Ankara Fabrics

Table 7 presents the distribution of the respondents according to the quality attributes of local *Ankara* fabrics. On a four-point scale of Excellent, Good, Fair and Poor. The result presented the responses made by the respondents regarding the qualities of local *Ankara* fabrics. In line with the respondents assessed, the weave of local *Ankara* fabrics are good ($\bar{x}=3.00$) and is ranked first, also air permeability of local *Ankara* fabrics is good and it was ranked second ($\bar{x}=2.87$), while good texture and fabric width ($\bar{x}=2.82$) ranked third, ($\bar{x}=2.81$), and have a decent colour fastness, feel and drape is good, they were both ranked fifth. Respondents also stated that the local *Ankara* fabric finish is good ($\bar{x}=2.76$) and was ranked seventh. Furthermore, the thread count and abrasive strength of the local *Ankara* fabrics are good, ($\bar{x}=2.75$) ranked eighth; meanwhile, the density of local *Ankara* fabrics ($\bar{x}=2.71$) is good and was ranked tenth. They also stated that the durability of local *Ankara* fabrics is good ($\bar{x}=2.70$), ranked eleventh. Additionally, respondents claimed that the fabric's weight of local *Ankara* is good, ($\bar{x}=2.65$), ranked twelfth, while their crease/wrinkle resistance ($\bar{x}=2.63$) is good and was consequently ranked thirteenth.

Table 7: Quality attributes of local Ankara fabrics (n=230)

S/ N	Fabric Quality	Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor	Mean	Decision	Rank
1	Weave	52(22.6)	124(53.9)	48(20.9)	6(2.6)	3.00	Good	1st
2	Colour Fastness	38(16.5)	118(51.3)	66(28.7)	8(3.5)	2.81	Good	5th
3	Thread Count	33(14.3)	116(50.5)	71(30.9)	10(4.3)	2.75	Good	8th
4	Durability	30(13.0)	116(50.4)	68(29.6)	16(7.0)	2.70	Good	11th
5	Abrasive Strength	37(16.1)	112(48.7)	68(29.6)	13(5.7)	2.75	Good	8th
6	Fabric Weight	40(17.4)	87(37.8)	86(37.4)	17(7.4)	2.65	Good	12th
7	Feel and Drape	46(20.0)	105(45.2)	67(29.1)	13(5.7)	2.81	Good	5th
8	Fabric Finish	36(15.7)	112(48.7)	73(31.7)	9(3.9)	2.76	Good	7th
9	Fabric Width	34(14.8)	124(53.9)	69(30.0)	3(1.3)	2.82	Good	3rd
10	Fabric Density	27(11.7)	120(52.1)	73(31.7)	10(4.3)	2.71	Good	10th
11	Texture	53(23.0)	96(41.7)	67(29.1)	14(6.1)	2.82	Good	3rd
12	Crease/ Wrinkle Resistance	26(11.3)	108(46.9)	81(35.2)	15(6.5)	2.63	Good	13th
13	Air Permeability	53(23.0)	106(46)	60(26.1)	11(4.8)	2.87	Good	2rd
14	Grand Mean					2.78		

Decision criteria: Excellent = 2.26 – 4.00, Good = 2.51 – 3.25, Fair = 1.76 – 2.50, Poor = 1.10 – 1.75, Mean of mean = 36.08 div 13 = **2.78**

3.1 Quality Attributes of Foreign Ankara Fabrics

Table 8 presents the responses made by the respondents regarding the qualities of foreign Ankara fabrics. According to the results, the respondents assessed the weave of imported Ankara fabrics' as excellent ($\bar{x}=3.45$) ranked it first. Additionally, the imported Ankara fabrics rank second for texture ($\bar{x}=3.38$), third for colour fastness ($\bar{x}=3.37$) and fourth for thread count ($\bar{x}=3.33$). Similarly, respondents stated that foreign Ankara fabrics had excellent durability ($\bar{x}=3.27$) ranked fifth, and good fabric finishes ($\bar{x}=3.23$), ranked sixth. Furthermore, the abrasive strength and fabric weight of foreign Ankara fabrics ($\bar{x}=3.20$) were ranked seventh respectively. The respondents stated that foreign Ankara fabrics have good fabric density ($\bar{x}=3.18$) and were ranked ninth. They also stated that foreign Ankara fabrics feel and drape well ($\bar{x}=3.16$), ranked tenth. Similarly, respondents stated that the fabric width and crease/wrinkle resistance ($\bar{x}=3.13$), is good, and that their air permeability ($\bar{x}=3.09$) is also good, placing it thirteenth in rank.

Table 8: Quality attributes of foreign Ankara fabrics (n=230)

s/ n	Fabric Quality	Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor	Mean	Decision	Rank
1	Weave	124(53.9)	89(38.7)	13(5.7)	4(1.7)	3.45	Excellent	1st
2	Colour Fastness	100(43.5)	117(50.9)	11(4.8)	2(.9)	3.37	Excellent	3rd
3	Thread Count	97(42.2)	112(48.7)	20(8.7)	1(.4)	3.33	Excellent	4th
4	Durability	95(41.3)	104(43)	30(13.0)	1(.4)	3.27	Excellent	5th
5	Abrasive Strength	80(34.8)	119(51.8)	27(11.7)	4(1.7)	3.20	Good	7th
6	Fabric Weight	81(35.2)	118(51.3)	28(12.2)	3(1.3)	3.20	Good	7th
7	Feel and Drape	80(34.8)	111(48.2)	35(15.2)	4(1.7)	3.16	Good	10th
8	Fabric Finish	92(40.0)	103(44.8)	31(13.5)	4(1.7)	3.23	Good	6th
9	Fabric Width	75(32.6)	115(50)	35(15.2)	4(1.7)	3.13	Good	11th
10	Fabric Density	80(34.8)	117(50.8)	27(11.7)	6(2.6)	3.18	Good	9th
11	Texture	115(50)	93(40.4)	16(7.0)	6(2.6)	3.38	Excellent	2nd
12	Crease/Wrinkle Resistance	70(30.4)	121(52.6)	37(16.1)	2(.9)	3.13	Good	11th
13	Air Permeability	74(32.2)	108(47)	43(18.7)	5(2.2)	3.09	Good	13th
14	Grand Mean					3.24		

Decision criteria: Excellent = 2.26 – 4.00, Good = 2.51 – 3.25, Fair = 1.76 – 2.50, Poor = 1.10 – 1.75, Grand Mean = $42.12 \div 13 = 3.24$

4 Conclusion and Recommendations

4.1 Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusion were drawn;

The majority of those surveyed knew that Ankara fabrics, both local and foreign, were perceived as good and excellent with decision criteria: good = 2.51 – 3.25 for local, while for foreign is excellent = 2.26 – 4.00 respectively. Additionally, both local and foreign Ankara fabrics were evaluated as having good and exceptional air permeability and texture, respectively, and good and excellent width and colour fastness. In order for the locally produced Ankara fabrics to compete with the imported ones in terms of weave, texture, colour fastness, and other characteristics, they should be encouraged. Importing foreign ones might not be necessary if these were accomplished. In order to support the local manufacturing sector and the emerging fashion designers, Ankara fabrics should be promoted among the civil servants as office wear across the federation. This would improve the standard of living.

4.2 Recommendations

Increasing cotton fiber cultivation by farmers in Nigeria would promote the production of higher quality Ankara fabrics by manufacturers, which could then be utilized by Nigerian workers. Additionally, the government should support cotton farmers by ensuring proper security for their farms to boost cotton production. Consequently, workers would benefit from this development. Employees are expected to have a positive perception of wearing local fabrics in the workplace, especially if mandated by legislation. Policies that promote the wearing of locally produced fabrics at least three times a week would be supported. This initiative would boost demand for local fabrics, resulting in more job openings for tailors and fashion designers, ultimately enhancing employment in the textile and fashion sectors. (Oni,

2025). assert that the policy statement of the Oyo State Government that mandated his civil/public servants to wear Aso-Oke and other traditional attires on Thursdays She hinted that the present administration in the state under the leadership of Engr. Seyi Makinde, FNSE approved the wearing of the Aso-Oke and other traditional attires on Thursdays for all civil/public servants to enhance the economy of the local fabric industries either through weaving, selling or sewing it.

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